

Toward a Practical Conceptualization of Discipleship: Education, the Great Commission and the Local Church

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ABSTRACT:

This article offers a practical framework for discipleship, rooted in extensive pastoral and academic experience, emphasizing its lifelong, communal, and contextual essence within the local church. It addresses challenges like cultural complexity and the post-COVID-19 discipleship gap, advocating for intentional disciple-making aligned with the Great Commission. Drawing on the Foursquare Global Council perspective and a 2022 leadership survey, discipleship is framed as a process of relational growth, transformation, learning, and missional engagement. The integration of formal and non-formal education is proposed as a vital tool for developing disciples and emerging leaders to fulfill the church's mandate to preach the gospel and make disciples.

Introduction

After twenty years pastoring and ten in academia, the need for continual engagement with the core mandate of the church keeps being of outmost importance. It is through my pastoral lens that as an author, I consider it necessary to bring light to this very important topic. In the following pages you will not find a highly theological inquiry, nor a theoretical proposition. This article will present my personal views and considerations based on experience that will begin to unfold a path toward a practical conceptualization of discipleship.

One challenge to discipleship is that it requires context and community. It is there, that new believers and seasoned Christians, create culture, share life, understand the biblical text, think about complex cultural issues, and are technically, *Discipled*. The reason I say a challenge, is because, I hear more and more people talk about discipleship as if it is something people can go through and become. A disciple never becomes, a disciple is! Let me explain what I mean by this, we all agree that, our

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journey into following Jesus starts, the moment we are born again.² Yes, I said, born again, I guess it is dated but it serves its purpose. In that moment, we are supposed to start our walk as followers, as disciples of Jesus Christ. In this journey there will be several lived experiences which include interaction with pastors, leaders, friends, church, events, professors, YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, X (formerly twitter), Tik Tok, Google, TV, books, the Bible, music, family, church programs, small group curriculum, discipleship training, college, seminary programs, political parties, and fill in the blank. There will be many things that will shape your thinking about God and his kingdom.

This is challenging because there is no, one-fits-all way to discipleship. It is highly dependent on who you are, the conversations you have, and the places or programs you attend. The Bible, of course, should be the primary tool for us to understand how to live for and follow Jesus, but the different voices and multiple interpretations could very much make discipleship a complex dilemma. This happens even though we might use the same bible translation, are members of the same denomination, or even attend the same church. Unfortunately, there are multiple views and opinions on how to follow Jesus, think about God, and fulfill his purposes.

Gary Matsdorf and the Global Council of The Foursquare Church³

As Global Education Coordinator for The Foursquare Church, Gary Matsdorf has dedicated his tenure to this very topic. In 2015, they conducted a thirty-five nation, National Strategic Assessment (NSA) which yielded valuable data, this included several findings, one of the core findings is tightly related to our topic “the need to become better at making disciples.”⁴ In this article, he substantially discusses discipleship and leadership development. Including a working definition of discipleship which can be useful for our conceptualization.

² John chapter three, Jesus and Nicodemus, born of the Spirit story.

³ The Global Council of The Foursquare Church has sixteen global elders, who are representative from around the world.

⁴ Gary Matsdorf. “Discipleship & Leadership Training” *WAPTE: Journal of the World Alliance of Pentecostal Theological Education* 8, no. 2 (2023): 187-198.

“A disciple is a believer in Christ who, together with others and by the Power of the Holy Spirit, intentionally pursues Jesus, is being changed by Jesus, and is actively engaged in the mission of Jesus.”⁵

Dr. Matsdorf, also believes that this definition includes important biblical elements such as the point where discipleship begins “after conversion” similar to what I mentioned, the moment we are born again. It also includes a spiritual component of what God, and the Holy Spirit does in us, and the continual following of Jesus through a lifetime journey of faith in Christ. This working definition helps us set the foundational tone for a Global Foursquare perspective on discipleship.

Educating and Disciple-Making⁶

On a quest to conceptualize discipleship, I was asked to speak on the subject of discipleship during the 2022 Foursquare Education Forum. In fact, the entire forum was dedicated to discipleship, and we were just coming out of the COVID-19 world-wide pandemic. Everyone was quite concerned with the way the church handled discipleship, in particular, as it pertains to following Jesus in the midst of difficulties and in this case a world crisis. The pandemic made us think more deeply about discipleship, Matlock and Kinnaman presenting research on the impact of the pandemic stated, “In many ways, the pandemic built a stronger case than ever for the need to strive toward disciple-making that produces individuals resistant to difficulties, turmoil and chaos.”⁷ Matlock added, “Church has to be more than a sermon, worship and what happens on the stage; that’s where people were seeing the discipleship deficit.” he continued, “I think the pandemic has definitely made everyone think about discipleship (or the lack of it) differently.” These were common conversations during and in the aftermath of COVID-19. Many have now forgotten about this, but I still think it is critical to consider what we experienced and what are we doing differently.

⁵ Gary Matsdorf, 2023, 190.

⁶ Presentation titled: Education + Discipleship in a Post Pandemic World. (Foursquare Education Forum. San Dimas California. 2022).

⁷ Mark Matlock & David Kinnaman. *ChurchPulse Weekly Conversations: Mark Matlock & David Kinnaman on Resilient Discipleship Post-COVID*. (Barna, 2021 3).

I want to remind our Foursquare and Pentecostal family that if we want to continue to be relevant and valuable for the kingdom, we need to unite in fulfilling God’s mission, which is the Great Commission. This means a renewed focus on evangelism and discipleship. Sister McPherson⁸ had a clear vision for this movement, a balance between evangelism and discipleship, between anointing and instruction, between the local church and world missions. Think about this! She was only 30 years old when the massive Angelus Temple was opened and dedicated. That same year she dedicated a disciple-making training institute, which today is Life Pacific University.⁹ She knew Sunday service was important, but weekly instruction and learning communities were as important to develop disciples. It was a combination of practical ministry, service, training, and a vision to save the lost, make disciples, and develop leaders to be sent into the field that kept the movement going.

We know that discipleship is not a program, a school, or head knowledge. It’s a process, a lifelong journey, of following Jesus. It is cyclical and includes things we do—as well as things we learn—and things we-learn-how-to-do—Disciples do not just learn to learn; disciples learn to live according to the Word. It is practical and theoretical, including praxis, the “doing what Jesus did” type of life, and theory, the deep thinking, “learning of and wresting with the Word of God” theology, and doctrine. It could include formal and informal ways of learning. It is doctrinal, theological, cultural, social, and personal. Christian discipleship must be deeply connected to the Bible and even more important to Jesus and the New Testament church. It is relational, the pandemic also made us think more about relationships, Mary Jankey, encourages post-pandemic discipleship by prioritizing “relationships over programs”¹⁰ This was common during that time when people were deprived from close contact

⁸ Founder of the International Church of the Foursquare Gospel (ICFG).

⁹ Formerly known as the Eco Park Evangelistic and Missionary Training Institute, later the Lighthouse of International Foursquare Evangelism (LIFE), then LIFE Bible College, and in 2019 it became Life Pacific University.

¹⁰ Mary Jankey. *Millennials & Gen Z Are Leaving Church. What Can We Do?* (Faithlife, 2021, 8).

with others, and in many cases not allowed to assembly for Sunday church.¹¹

Common Language for Discipleship

In one of their books *Faith for Exiles*, Barna Research attempted to bring common language to discipleship. Some of the core aspects presented were, to develop Jesus followers, who are resiliently faithful in the face of cultural coercion, and who live a vibrant life in the Spirit.¹² I also worked on research of my own, I sent out a very short survey with the following questions; 1) In one sentence or paragraph, what is your personal definition of discipleship (disciple-making) and why?, and 2) In one sentence or paragraph, what is the role of education in the body of Christ? Or is there any real value in education for the mission of God? The survey was sent to a selected group of high-level denominational leaders in the US Foursquare Church who held key executive roles. This was purposely done to understand how these core group of elected or appointed leaders of the denomination define discipleship. Interestingly, we all have our own ideas and definitions of discipleship, most of these leaders sent a paragraph or two, some sent just a sentence, some were more theological others highly practical. All could be correct to some degree, but it could be confusing for someone to understand what Foursquare means when we talk about discipleship. The following were some common themes I gather from all the data, by analyzing themes and similarities. It was great to discover a pivotal finding, everyone connected discipleship to a process and not a program, which indicates this is something we all agree upon

Based on this, here are four commonalities to help us bring common language as it pertains to discipleship within Foursquare:

1. Growing in relationship with Jesus and with others.
2. Being transformed into his image.
3. Embarking on a journey of learning and growth.
4. Becoming kingdom focused (missional).

¹¹ Every state had their individual regulations, and some countries were more strict than other, nevertheless, everyone experienced a level of impact from the 2020 worldwide pandemic.

¹² Kinnaman, David, Mark Matlock, and Aly Hawkins. *Faith for Exiles: 5 Ways for a New Generation to Follow Jesus in Digital Babylon*. (Baker Books, 2019, 33).

Another question we need to ask is related to the more practical, the how? not the what? How do we promote growth and develop disciples? Is education (learning) important? Is it connected to discipleship? The response is clear; we must be intentional! Jesus was intentional in calling his disciples and working personally on their development, growth, and learning. We cannot delegate discipleship! It is not a program we can appoint a pastor to oversee. It is a way of life, a journey with Jesus, and helping others follow him as well. Paul was intentional in developing disciples like Titus, Timothy, and others, you and I must be intentional as well. Pastors, leaders, and churches, should be intentional in making disciples.

Jesus' role as a teacher shows the value of intentional disciple-making in the spiritual transformation of people. One of his roles was in the form of a teacher to train disciples with content and information, but without neglecting the spiritual and supernatural (miracles, signs, wonders). It was both informative and practical; it was learning from Jesus and doing the supernatural work of the Father. Building common language around discipleship is important to bring clarity and direction. As a denomination, there are elements that unite us and keep us focused on a shared path. Discipleship is such a core element of the church and thus we should consider common language at the very least. We might not all agree on how it looks like or how it should be properly done, but we can all agree on common language around discipleship and even more importantly, that it is central to the work of Jesus, the New Testament church, and our Pentecostal movement.

Matthew 28:18-20

These verses encompass the Great Commission, and it has been core to disciple-making throughout generations. Jesus dies on the cross and rises from the dead to then appears to his disciples. He spent forty days with them and before ascending into heaven, he gives them this final mandate. This passage is the basis for thousands of people answering the call to ministry, to go into the ends of the world and proclaim the gospel of Jesus Christ. For some Bible scholars, the Great Commission is the universal mission of the Church. It is the mandate of the Lord for his Church to fulfill his mission.

The mission is very clear, preach the gospel and make disciples.¹³ Moreover, Greenway makes an obvious but powerful observation, stating that each of the four gospels ends with the *Great Commission*. It was so critical for the original writers and for the Holy Spirit to make sure it was included as Jesus final mandate.¹⁴

I believe the main reason we exist as a church is for evangelism and disciple-making, we don't make disciples to establish a church, we establish a church to make disciples. The difference is significant; in the first statement we can fall into the mistake of reaching people and trying to make disciples to maintain a church or gather a group of people. In the second statement, the reason for establishing a church is for the sole purpose of making disciples. One has the individual as its mission, the other has the organization as its mission.

It is common understanding that the mission of the church is to make disciples and not simply to do worship services, meetings, events, etc. However, we place greater emphasis on our Sunday meetings and events than on our formation processes, spiritual development, educational or discipleship strategies. What is your discipleship strategy? How do disciples develop in your church? If you can't answer these two questions, it's because your focus is more on Sunday worship service than on developing disciples, followers of Jesus. The Great Commission must be ingrained in your life. Sunday worship is not the ultimate goal of the church, nor the measure of a congregation's spirituality or maturity.

The Discipleship Intent

Pastors and churches cannot lose sight of the fact that the purpose of their lives and ministries is to fulfill this mandate—To proclaim the gospel and make disciples of Jesus (Followers) in Jerusalem, Judea, Samaria, and to the ends of the earth. For example, Paul was one of the great pioneers in the advancement of the gospel to the whole world. His mission-mindset demonstrated the commitment and passion he had to take this message

¹³ Carson, Donald Arthur, RT, Frans, Alex Motyer & Gordon, Wenham. *New Bible Commentary: 21st Century Edition*. (Inter-Varsity Press, 1994).

¹⁴ Greenway, Roger S. *Go and Make Disciples!: An Introduction to Christian Missions*. (P&R Publishing, 1999).

beyond his local church, but Paul was not only an evangelist, apostle, and preacher, he was also great at making disciples, born again believers, followers of the Messiah. Wherever he planted a church, he wasn't just thinking about preaching a sermon or planning Sunday activities to gather a crowd, he was in search of new believers, and people who would begin taking on responsibility in the new established churches. He would appoint elders and train young pastors like Titus and Timothy. He was into developing people and helping them understand this new life, a lifelong journey following Jesus to do his work on earth.

We can also see how even in the letter to Titus, he left him in charge of continuing to establish elders (disciples) to take over his responsibilities. In Titus 1:5, not only did he develop Titus, but he now expected him to develop others. For Paul, discipleship was key as he understood that he would not be in those places for long. This mentality made him quick to identify potential leaders and began a process of discipleship and formation so that when the time came for his departure, these leaders would be ready not only to maintain what he had started, but to continue advancing the work in that region.

Formative Years—A Culture of Discipleship

I do believe the church, the *ekklēsia*,¹⁵ or the gathering of the saints is a powerful place for people to understand their relationship with Jesus and how to follow him. The first few years as a new believer are critical for this new journey. These are the formative years, similar to the time when a child begins cognitive and social development, when new Christians, new Christians are learning the foundations of their newfound faith in Jesus. I remember a true story of a 16-year-old young man who came with his mom, and both got saved at church. I was a young pastor in my late 20s and full of passion for the Lord. After several months attending Sunday and Wednesday church services, he came up to the front at the end of the service and asked if this was it (going to church). “Is this it?”, “Is this all we must do?”. “Is there anything else?” This crushed me inside; it left me speechless.

¹⁵ See Strongs G1577 *ekklēsia* at Blue Letter Bible here
<https://www.blueletterbible.org/lexicon/g1577/kjv/tr/0-1/>

I knew exactly what he was saying, even at that young age and being a new believer, he asked a very profound question that changed my entire view of what it means to be a Christian. That conversation led me to start all kinds of ways for people to walk their journey. I even wrote a small book for new believers, where I tell his story, as a way to explain that following Jesus is much more than attending church, but unfortunately, that is what we have been unintentionally teaching people that it means. To the contrary, we walk the journey of a lifetime, we follow Jesus, we serve, we respond to his calling, we learn and study, we cultivate a deeper relationship with him, we begin taking on leadership roles, we speak to others about Jesus, we train others into ministry and so much more. It is a way of life!

From Disciple-Making to Developing Leaders in the Local Church¹⁶

The Purpose Driven Church movement in the 1990 claimed to give pastors the tools to have healthy growing churches, and part of the strategy was to have some kind of basic discipleship process, or assimilation process for new believers or church visitors. According to the author, it is an effective way to help people join the church, feel welcome and become part of the new church.¹⁷ Barna Research asserts that effective churches create their own pipelines to develop disciples and leaders.¹⁸ It is important for the church to develop disciples who at one point could begin the process of development into emerging leaders. As we have stated, discipleship is not a program, but a process, and having intentional developmental processes can certainly be vital for the continual emergence of leaders. These processes include education and training, similar to how leadership roles and promotions are given in the business world. One of these tools that can serve as part of a process is, informal education. If well organized in our local communities, Informal trainings and educational opportunities could be one of the quickest mechanism or organic process for the formation and

¹⁶ Daniel, Ruarte, "Liderazgo y Iglesia: Principios Efectivos para Pastores y Líderes Latinos." (Asociación Teológica Hispana, Mottelbello, CA. 2019).

¹⁷ Rick Warren, *The Purpose Driven Church: Growth Without Compromising Your Message & Mission*(Zondervan. 1995)

¹⁸ Barna, George. *The Habits of Highly Effective Churches: Being Strategic in Your God-Given Ministry.* (Gospel Light Publications, 2000).

development of leaders. For example, the church where I became a Christian and grew up as a new believer did this very well. Why? Because many people came to Christ during those years, and second because there were many who were given informal educational opportunities. Several people from that medium size church became lifelong disciples and emerging leaders in the church. Fast forward, three decades later, I am one of those leaders, and I know many of the youth and young adults that grew up in that church who are now pastoring, leading worship, serving at different organizations, ministries, and even at the district or denominational level. This was not a mega church, nor did it have a large facility, or many business leaders. God must have been doing something there, and it was evident by the many people turning their life to Christ and willing to follow him.

In addition to having many activities, events, services and ministries, something that caught my attention was the discipleship and training process this church had established. Now I understand this is informal education, but at that time I was just a new believer who wanted to grow and learn more about God and his Word. First-time visitors or new converts were encouraged to participate in a class for new members, basic topics were discussed such as for the life of a new believer, salvation, community life, the Bible, baptism, and others. A place where there was dialogue, and we were encouraged to ask many questions. Then, they had the option of continuing to take additional classes at a more advanced level, always on a voluntary basis, systematic growth was emphasized but maintaining a focus on practical topics for the life of a relatively new believer or someone with a desire to become more actively involved in the life of the local church and the Great Commission. We were taught how to use the Bible and a foundational overview of the different books, topics, and characters of the Old and New Testaments. The last step in this process was a structured one-year vocational program, what I personally called a *pre-institute*, it was a church-led program, but it was not called a Bible institute. It was biblical, theological and ministerial training for those who wished to grow deeper in the ministry vocation and service. Unlike the other levels, this last year had a minimal financial cost and required the purchase of additional books in some of the classes. They began to require us to do

homework and to be responsible in attendance and participation. This entire process coupled with practical ministry service, was organically used to make disciples, and develop emerging leaders.

This process would take about two to three years, during this time you connected to the local church, served in the local church, experienced community among peer students, and a strong connection to the teachers, pastors and church leaders. There were lots of opportunities to ask questions or make comments, which was not possible during a Sunday morning sermon. At the end of the process, pastors and teachers placed great emphasis on continuing our studies in more formal ways, for example, Bible college or seminary. Personally, I highly benefited from it, and it is the reason I am who I am and do what I do today. I would have not pursued higher education if it were not for the ministry of that local church, and particularly this disciple-making process. The process continues, it does not end with one class or experience, it is a lifelong process of being a disciple.

Formal and Non-Formal Educational Model

One aspect of discipleship is the notion of learning which is connected to educational processes. Understanding this can help us value the work of the local church in establishing non-formal educational processes to make disciples and develop emerging leaders. These educational pathways can provide the needed framework to support a lifelong journey of discipleship. On the other side formal educational models should also be kept in mind as a way to further and deepened the growth of a disciple. In this section, the formal and non-formal educational model is presented (see figure 1).

This model is important to mention as we think about the relationship between the local church and Bible colleges or theological seminaries. This model has two circles, a large one that symbolizes the large number of individuals who are developed through informal education, similar to the process I shared above in my own personal journey. The small circle refers to those who, after going through non-formal educational processes, wish to continue their development through formal degree programs. According to Dr. Eaton, formal education is that which represents endorsed or accredited degrees that are valid to obtain such certifications by external entities. Degrees from these institutions are

recognized and validated by external companies, government institutions, and professional associations that certify the validity of these degrees.¹⁹ Non-formal/informal education and development are more experimental and practical, it is to some extent vocational in nature. This type of education is very valuable and has its place in the formation of the leader. Every year there are thousands and thousands of intensive seminars, workshops, trainings, conferences, and events that have elements of learning and growth, but at the same time are considered informal education. These in most cases are less expensive and flexible in terms of requirements, demands, and homework. Informal and formal educational processes have been key in the development and growth of individuals for many years. For this reason, in ecclesiastical contexts, we take the time to learn and study the word of God formally or informally. Let's look at the following (Figure 1) to better understand this concept and then explain it.

Figure 1. *Formal and non-formal education model*

¹⁹ Eaton, Sarah Elaine. *Formal, Non-Formal and Informal Learning: The Case of Literacy, Essential Skills, and Language* (Learning in Canada. 2010).

There are jobs in which employers ask not only for a graduation diploma but for academic transcripts to be certain of the quality of the degree and make sure the student completed the program at an accredited institution. To be a chaplain in a hospital, Navy, Army, and other institution, most of the time they ask that candidates have a valid master's degree awarded by an accredited institution. In some cases, it is not required but that is not the norm. To teach at a formal educational institution, they ask for academic transcripts from the university where prospective teaching candidates graduated to verify the accreditation of these institutions and the validity of the degree.

The Great Commission requires a commitment to growth, learning, and education. Non-formal education or formal education are simply tools to support the lifelong journey of discipleship. We want to make sure there is continual growth in our life and ministry skills. Either in a formal or informal way disciples should always be learning and growing. Becoming lifelong learners!

Final Thoughts

In our quest toward a conceptualization of discipleship as Foursquare Pentecostal leaders, let us not forget, the Global Council working definition stated by Dr. Matsdorf and the four commonalities gathered in 2022 from some of our top leaders around the nation.

Working Definition: “A disciple is a believer in Christ who, together with others and by the power of the Holy Spirit, intentionally pursues Jesus, is being changed by Jesus, and is actively engaged in the mission of Jesus.”²⁰

Common Language: Discipleship is not a program, but a process, and has to do with: 1) Growing in relationship with Jesus and with others, 2) being transformed into his image, 3) embarking on a journey of learning and growth, and 4) becoming kingdom focused (missional).

²⁰ Gary Matsdorf, 2023, 190.

As we consider the challenges and opportunities this topic brings let us be reminded that discipleship should always be an exciting and relevant topic of discussion for Christians who understand the value of the Great Commission and the importance of evangelism and disciple-making for Jesus and his followers.